

TRANSLATION THEORY AND ITS MAIN PROBLEMS

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Abstract. Translation is a tool that serves as the interests of friendship, brotherhood and cooperation between different peoples, as well as the expansion of economic, political, scientific, cultural and literary ties between them. As the field of linguistics is developing, translation is considered as one of the most important part in this sphere. Translation is learned by the subject of ‘the theory of translation’. Many scientists investigated this theory thus finding its problems also. So this article focuses on the background of translation, such as how linguists defined the translation, some problems of it and analyze them carefully by giving some examples.

Keywords: principles of the translation, international federation, bilingual system, harmonization, lingual and cultural views.

Translation theory shares a number of concerns with what is commonly called *communication theory*. Perhaps the most important observation which the communication theorists have produced for translators is the recognition that *every act of communication has three dimensions: Speaker (or author), Message, and Audience*. The more we can know about the original author, the actual message produced by that author, and the original audience, the better acquainted we will be with that particular act of communication.

Translation is a process of rendering a text, written piece or a speech by means of other languages. The difference of translation from retelling or other kinds of transfer of a given text is that that translation is a process of creating an original unity in contexts and forms of original.

The translation quality is defined by its completeness and value. “The completeness and value of translation means definite rendering of the contextual sense of the original piece and a high-grade functional-stylistic conformity¹”.

The questions of linguistic difficulties of literary translation are partially discussed on the basis of native and foreign scientist’s works such as Barkhudarov L.S., Komissarov V.N., Garbovski N.K., Breus E.V., Yashina N.K.², etc.

The concept “high-grade functional-stylistic conformity” clearly points on two existing ways of rendering the form in unity with the meaning: the first one is a reproduction of specific features of the form of the original piece and the second one is the creation of functional conformities of those features.

It means when translating the specific features of an original literature we should rather consider the style inherent for the given genre but than direct copying the form of an original. While translating, we should also remember that different lexical and grammatical elements of an original might be translated differently if accepted by the norms of conformity to the whole original.

An awareness of this tri-partite character of communication can be very useful for interpreters. Assuming that an act of communication is right now taking place, as you read what I wrote, there are three dimensions to this particular act of communication: myself, and what I am intending to communicate; the actual words, which are on this page; and what you understand me to be saying. When

¹ <https://www.refine.com.ru/pageid-1239-2.html>

² Бархударов, Л. С. (1975). Язык и перевод/Леонид Степанович Бархударов. М.: Международные отношения, 240.; Бархударов Л.С., Семко С. А. (1990). Основные вопросы теории и практики перевода. школа, 45.; Komissarov, V. N. (1991). Language and culture in translation: Competitors or collaborators. *traduction, terminologie, redaction*, 4(1).; Гарбовский, Н. К. (2018). Теория перевода: учебник и практикум для академического бакалавриата. ЭБС Юрайт [сайт].-URL: <https://urait.ru/bcode/422777/>(дата обращения: 10.01. 2021).; Бреус, Е. В. (2003). Теория и практика перевода с английского языка на русский. Изд-во УРАО.; Yashina, N. K. (2020). The modeling of the translation process in the cognitive aspect. *Международный научно-исследовательский журнал*, (8 (98) Часть 3), 93-97.

the three dimensions converge, the communication has been efficient.

Translation is inherently a difficult activity. Translators can face problems, which make the process even more difficult, such as:

Problems with the text:

- The source text not being the final text, and being redrafted during the translation process of illegible text or misspelt text or incomplete text or Poorly written text;

- Missing references in the text (e.g. the translator is to translate captions to missing photos)

Language problems:

- Dialect terms and neologisms
- Unexplained acronyms and abbreviations
- Unreasonably obscure jargon
- Other:
- Highly specific cultural references.

The question of whether particular words are untranslatable is often debated, with lists being produced from time to time. For example, it is hard to find a noun corresponding to the Russian *почемучка* (pochemuchka) or the Uzbek *чойхона* (Choykhona), but the adjectives «inquisitive» and «jinxed» correspond just fine.

The words that present the most problems for translation are often the small, common words. For example, the verb «to get» in all its various uses covers nearly seven columns of the most recent version of the Robert-Collins French-English dictionary³. The same is true for most apparently simple, common words, such as «go» (seven columns), «come» (four and a half columns), and so forth.

³ <https://eduq.info/xmlui/handle/11515/12977>

Cultural aspects can render translation problematic. Consider the example of a word like «bread». At first glance, it is a very simple word, referring in everyday use to just one thing, with obvious translations into other languages. But ask people from England, France and China to describe or draw «bread», they have different imagination and give different definitions concerning the word “bread”.

The problem often lies in failure to distinguish between translation and equivalent (word-usually one) give a short: Glossing is what a glossary does. Glossing is decoding meaning and intent at the, as explained above translation.

Target language are hard to gloss into a single other word, but given two or more words, they can be perfectly adequately translated. «Bread» has a better claim to being untranslatable, since even if we resort to saying «French bread», «Chinese bread», «Uzbek bread», etc. We are relying on our audience knowing what these are like.

Differing levels of precision also play a role. What does «there» mean? Even discounting idiomatic uses such as «there, there, don't cry», we can be confronted by several possibilities.

Linguists are naturally enthusiastic about obscure words with local flavour, and are wont to declare them «untranslatable», but in reality these incredibly culture-laden terms are the easiest of all to translate, even more so than universal concepts such as «mother». This is because it is standard practice to translate these words by the same word in the other language, borrowing it for the first time if necessary.

The more obscure and specific to a culture the term is, the simpler it is to translate. For example, the name of an insignificant settlement such as Europe in Australia is automatically just «Europe» in every language in the world that uses the Roman alphabet, whilst it takes some knowledge to be aware that *Saragossa* is *Zaragoza*, *Saragosse*, etc. or that *China* is *Cina*, *Chine*, and so forth.

Expressions may also exist in one language, which refer to concepts that don't exist in another language. For example, the French «tutoyer»' and «vouvoyer» would both be translated into English as «to address as 'you'«, since the singular informal second person pronoun is archaic in English. (On the other hand, depending on the context, the meaning of the French word «tutoyer», or Spanish «tutear», could be translated as «to be on first name terms with».)

Indeed, one of the main rules in translation is to «keep the context», but isn't the language of the document itself the heart of the context that should be kept?

Another serious problem of translation is that translating can be described as writing what you have read in another language. And yet how can one expect that the translator perfectly understands the original author? While this is the translator's job, it is the author who is praised for the work; but can a translation of Asimov be considered as Asimov's work? Could translation even be seen as «legal plagiarism»?

As the goal of translation is to establish a relationship of equivalence between the source and the target texts – that is to say, both texts communicate the same message – while taking into account the various constraints placed on the translator, a successful translation can be judged by two criteria:

1. Faithfulness, also called fidelity, that is the extent to which the translation accurately renders the meaning of the source text, without adding to it or subtracting from it, and without intensifying or weakening any part of the meaning;
2. Transparency, that is the extent to which the translation appears to a native speaker of the target language to have originally been written in that language, and conforms to the language's grammatical, syntactic and idiomatic conventions[6;78].

A translation meeting the first criterion is said to be a «faithful translation»; a translation meeting the second criterion is said to be an «idiomatic translation».

The criteria used to judge the faithfulness of a translation vary according to the subject, the precision of the original contents, the type, function and use of the text, its literary qualities, its social or historical context, for example.

The criteria for judging the transparency of a translation would appear more straightforward: an unidiomatic translation «sounds» wrong, and in the extreme case of word-for-word translations generated by many machine translation systems, often result in patent nonsense.

Nevertheless, in certain contexts a translator may knowingly strive to produce a literal translation. For example, literary translators and translators of religious works often adhere to the source text as much as possible. To do this they deliberately «stretch» the boundaries of the target language to produce an unidiomatic text. Likewise, a literary translator may wish to adopt words or expressions from the source language to provide «local colour» in the translation.

The concepts of fidelity and transparency are looked at differently in recent translation theories. The idea that acceptable translations should be as creative and original as their source text is gaining momentum in some quarters.

The concepts of fidelity and transparency remain strong in Western traditions. They are not necessarily as prevalent in non-western traditions. For example, the Indian epic Ramayana has numerous versions in many Indian languages and the stories in each are different from one another. If one looks into the words used for translation in Indian (either Aryan or Dravidian) languages, the freedom given to the translators is evident.

The study of science behind the human languages is called linguistics. It involves the analysis of where the language originated from, what was the need, how it evolved with time, recent developments and future possibilities. The creation of a perfectly defined language by which we can communicate to one

another is one of the most relevant reasons to separate us from rest of the members in the animal kingdom. The importance of language is not hidden from anybody and hence linguistics is a very important field of study.

Cognitive sciences, on the other hand, deal basically with studying any process or event from mental perspective i.e. it believes all the activities or happenings around us is the result of some phenomena going on in the brain and the analysis of that detail and other details is what we study in cognitive sciences. Now where does linguistics come under the scanner of cognitive science?

Linguistics has been taken up as a field of research in cognitive science, as the evolution of language and its continuous development is because of some processes taking place in mind. For example thinking to speak or communicate, taking initiative to talk, finding some tools or objects to communicate, etc., all are related to cognition i.e. related to mind and its various processes.

Linguistics and cognitive sciences is an important branch of science and it has led to various discoveries regarding the language development. How is the accent of any language or the body of its words are generated and what it takes for any mind to adapt to it.

The study of languages is not easy, and even more complex is the process of language learning. A new born baby starts to learn basic words few weeks after birth and masters basic form of it in few years without any training just by listening. Generally all of us are able to adopt and use a language proficiently under normal circumstances. Have you ever wondered why it is simple to learn the first language as a baby than to learn a new language when we become adult or what is the limit to which any language can be learned and understood by us? All such questions can be answered by cognitive studies of the languages.

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